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Development of lightweight aggregate concrete with optimum thermal transmittance for opaque wall assembly in composite climates

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Introduction: For making energy- efficient buildings; lightweight aggregate concrete (LWAC) using different lightweight aggregates (LWA) are used such as vermiculite, oil palm shell, perlite, lightweight expanded clay aggregate (LECA), pumice etc. (1). The main objective of the presented study was to develop eco-efficient LWAC using LECA after optimization for their packing density along with optimization of aggregate content, w/c ratio, SP %, slump and cement content. After optimizing each of the above parameter; different kind of physico mechanical and thermal properties were determined, and then one final optimized LWAC mix were suggested having desired attributes, as per ACI 213 and Energy Conservation Building Code (ECBC) 2017 recommendations.

Methods: OPC-43, sand and superplasticizer (SP) were selected as primary raw materials to develop LWAC. Aggregate used in this study was LECA of different sizes fractions i.e. 0 – 2 mm, 2 – 8 mm and 8 – 15 mm. These aggregates were used for the experimental work after physico-chemical characterization. Specimens were cast and tested after 7 and 28 days when curing process is over. Three types of curing conditions (moist, water dip and air curing) were taken. In the study, three types of cases were taken to get the final optimized mix proportion viz.- case 1- shows the aggregate and w/c ratio optimization, case 2- shows the SP % and slump value optimization and case 3- shows the cement optimization.

Results & Discussions: Slump, compressive- flexural strength, drying shrinkage and thermal conductivity (k-value) was calculated after 28 days of curing (Figure 1). Mix MS- 3 (w/c: 0.40, SP: 0.78 and LECA of 325 kg/m³ (0- 2 mm: 30%, 2- 8 mm: 40%, 8- 15 mm: 30%)) showed the slump within the permissible limits (12 to 15 mm). The same mix showed maximum 28 days compressive strength (24.5 MPa), flexural strength (3.25 MPa) and minimum drying shrinkage (-0.03%) in which cement content was 400 kg/m³. Also, thermal conductivity of the optimized LWAC mix was obtained as 0.230 W/m.K, which was lower than other LWAC mixes and normal weight concrete (1).

Figure 1. Set up (a) Flexural strength; (b) Drying shrinkage

Conclusions: It was inferred that without adding any strength improving admixtures; it was possible to produce LWAC having compressive strength of 23.9 MPa and flexural strength of 3.4 MPa. Incorporation of LECA in the mix increased thermal insulation property of LWAC which makes the building as energy efficient envelope. Thermal transmittance (U-value) was obtained as 0.31 W/m²K which was less than 0.40 W/m²K, as per ECBC 2017. Thus, it was concluded that the developed LWAC composite can be used as opaque wall assembly in composite climates which will provide higher degree of thermal insulation along with reduction in dead load for superstructures.

Keywords: Sustainable concrete, Lightweight aggregates, Light expanded clay aggregate, Thermal conductivity.

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